

THE MODELS OF JUDICIAL CONSTITUTIONAL CONTROL IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES AND THE EXPERIENCE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The present article reviews the main constitutional models such as American and European, comparing the advantages and disadvantages of constitutional justice, including the system of constitutional judicial control of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: constitution, judicial constitutional control, models of judicial constitutional control, American model, European model.

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада асосий конституциявий моделлар, шу жумладан Америка ва Европа моделлари кўриб чиқилган. Таҳлиллар асосида конституциявий одил судловнинг афзалликлари ва камчиликлари, шунингдек, Ўзбекистон Республикасидаги конституциявий суд назорати тизими фаолияти қиёсий ўрганилган.

Калит сўзлар: конституция, конституциявий суд назорати, конституциявий суд назорати моделлари, Америка модели, Европа модели.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются основные конституционные модели, такие как американская и европейская, сравниваются преимущества и недостатки конституционного правосудия, в том числе системы конституционного судебного контроля Республики Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: конституция, судебный конституционный контроль, модели судебного конституционного контроля, американская модель, европейская модель.

In a modern democratic state, the constitutional control body plays a crucial role, since it is within its competence to check the conformity of the constitution, normative acts, as well as the actions of state bodies, officials and other subjects of constitutional legal relations. The existence of a well-developed system of constitutional justice is one of the signs of an advanced democratic state. The protection of the foundations of the state that are enshrined in its constitution is one of the most important and urgent goals for today.

Considering the issue of the constitutional control body, first of all, it should be noted that its nature de-

pends entirely on one or another model. Thus, today there are two main models: American and European. A number of legal scholars also distinguish Islamic, socialist and mixed models. Nevertheless, the dichotomous division is the most accepted and acknowledged in the world.

The American model of constitutional control exists in more than 40 countries. This model is characterised by administering justice by courts of general jurisdiction, such as in the US, or exclusively by the Supreme Court, this practice is applied in Australia and India¹.

¹ See: Блохин П. Д. Защита основных прав средствами конституционного правосудия в Германии // Сравнительное конституционное обозрение. 2014. №3. – С. 81–105.

Basically, the American model is characterised by the following main features:

Firstly, it is comprehensive in nature, as it includes, in addition to legal acts, also the actions of the subjects of constitutional-legal relations. Secondly, it is characterized by decentralization, i.e. exercising control by any court, which is the reason why the American model is often referred to as decentralized. However, in our view, this is not quite correct, as in countries with the American model, exercising constitutional control exclusively by the Supreme Court or supreme bodies of state power (Japan, Brazil, India) such a name is not acceptable. In these countries, on the contrary, the system is centralised. Third, there is a limitation of the circle of subjects to whom the decisions of the supervisory bodies apply, as they are binding only on the participants of the process. Moreover, a characteristic feature of constitutional control in countries with a federal system is that each state has its own system of courts that are entitled to exercise such control.

In addition to the above-mentioned features of the American model, it can be noted that this system is characterised by subsequent and specific control². This means that in a case, any of the parties can argue that the law is not compatible with the constitution. In this case, the process of examining the case is interrupted, while the constitutionality of the law is being examined. The law is formally in force during the period of review until it is repealed.

In addition, another name for the American model is often found in literature, so-called – the diffuse model. Most scholars are convinced that the name “diffuse” model is more revealing of its essence. In proving their point of view, they cite the following arguments: first, that this model is widespread not only in countries with the Anglo-Saxon legal system but also in a number of other countries, such as Portugal; second, that the consideration of a particular case is carried out by courts of general jurisdiction and not by a single body as in the European model.

It should be also noted that the American model of judicial control allows for wider use of the judicial

system, giving the opportunity to appeal on specific issues to both lower courts and the Supreme court. As P. Hogg writes, “Judicial review of legislation can be exercised in any proceeding, at any level of the courts. All bodies exercising judicial power have a right, and a duty, to control the efficiency of legislation when the question arises in the proceedings they conduct³. While the U.S. Constitution does not create an institution of constitutional control, the Supreme Court set a precedent in the famous 1803 case of *Williams Mabury* against the Secretary of State, Madison for patenting a justice of the peace by President J. Adams shortly before the end of his term.

After President T. Jefferson took office, and the new Secretary of State refused to issue a patent to *Marbury*. The appellant, in his petition to the Supreme Court, requested to recognize his right to the position of squire and make an order pursuant to the Judiciary Act of 1789. The Supreme Court, in its decision, recognised *Marbury*’s right to be a squire but refused to make the order. The Supreme Court found the judicial organisation act mentioned as a legal basis, was partially unconstitutional. The initiator of this decision was Chief Judge J. Marshall, who believed that only a Court has the power to reveal what the law is and only a court has the power to declare the law invalid.

In considering the procedural question of whether a law was consistent with the Constitution, Marshall obtained the approval of Congress and the President to this conclusion of the Supreme Court. There through this in effect confirmed the right of the Supreme Court to exercise control over the constitutionality of the acts of the supreme bodies of the State⁴.

Currently, the Supreme Court has the conclusive opinion on the constitutionality of laws passed by Congress or state legislatures. Since the Supreme Court acted as a watchdog, over 100 acts have been declared unconstitutional, most of them constituting state legislation.

However still, in the USA, all courts, federal and state, have constitutional control functions within their competence. Any court in the US has the power to strike down a law if it is unconstitutional, and it

² See: Вересова Н.А. Нормотворческая функция Федерального Конституционного суда ФРГ и Конституционного суда РФ (сравнительно-правовой анализ). URL: <http://lawtheses.com/normotvorcheskaya-funktsiya-federalnogo-konstitutsionnogo-sudafederativnoy-respubliki-germanii-i-konstitutsionnogo-suda-#ixzz4Z2wI9Rj3> Датаобращения:18.02.2017.

³ Constitutional Law of Canada: 2021 Student Edition.

⁴ United States Constitution [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <http://www.hist.msu.ru/ER/Etext.htm> (date of the application: 12.07.2016).

may issue an opinion on the constitutionality or unconstitutionality of any legal action, i.e. the trial of a criminal or civil case is interrupted and consideration of the constitutionality of the law is started.

But only the Supreme court decides on unconstitutionality, which is binding on all lower courts. If a law is declared unconstitutional by the Supreme court, it effectively loses its effect, as it cannot henceforth be applied by the courts or other organs of the state. It should be noted that, apart from reviewing the constitutionality of statutory acts, the Supreme Court may also interpret the US Constitution and existing laws. The act of interpretation of the Supreme Court is binding on all courts in the country.

A number of other countries which have followed the US model are also noteworthy. For instance, the Constitution of Ireland, Article 26 provides that the President has the power, after consultation with the Council of State, to refer any draft legislation to the Supreme Court to determine whether it or any particular provision of it, violates the Constitution or any of its provisions. In all cases where the Supreme Court of Ireland decides that a provision of a bill is contrary to the Constitution, the President must refuse to sign such a bill.

An analysis of Swiss law shows that the Swiss Federal Court decides, among other things, on disputes over competence and state law disputes between various levels of government, on complaints about violations of the constitutional rights of citizens, as well as on complaints from private persons about violations of concordats and State contracts (articles 106-114 of the Constitution). In the semi-canton of Basel, the administrative courts exercise constitutional justice, and in the semi-canton of Nidwalden, the Supreme court. The only constitutional court in Switzerland has existed in the canton of Jura since 1978 and it has the right to invalidate acts of the cantonal parliament at the request of the cantonal government. In the Kingdom of Norway, the Supreme Court, at the request of the Storting (Parliament), issues an opinion on legal questions (§83 of the Constitution). In Estonia, constitutional control is performed by the Constitutional Control Board of the Supreme Court, which

consists of judges elected by the Plenum of the Court for a term of five years.

Thus, in the analysed countries, constitutional control is not carried out by specialised courts, but by the ordinary courts, which allows for wider use of the judicial system.

In addition to the so-called American model, there is also the European model of constitutional control, or the continental model, which only became widespread in the first half of the last century. The European model was theoretically justified by positivists who identified right and law. An elaborate justification, within the framework of the positivist understanding of the law, was defined by the German scientist Kelsen. In his doctrine of law, he started from the premise that law is a normative order, a system of norms that regulate certain social relations⁵. The norms have a certain hierarchical structure: superior and inferior. To ensure this order, and most importantly to achieve subordination of the lower norms to higher ones, a special institution of control is needed, whose competence will include the recognition of norms as compliant with the general law, the norms of which have supreme legal force⁶.

The essence of this model is that constitutional control is exercised by a special body, for example, in the Russian Federation it is the Constitutional Court, in Spain, it is the Constitutional Tribunal, in France it is a quasi-judicial body – the Constitutional Council. The main feature of this model is that the specialized body of the constitutional control is an autonomous element of the judiciary, i.e. it is not part of the general system of the judiciary. The decisions of this body are final and, therefore, not subject to appeal⁷.

In our opinion, another peculiarity is that this model is characterized by a preliminary, abstract and mandatory control. As a result, constitutional control is comprehensive, holistic and, most importantly, coherent.

Under the Austrian Constitution, the courts do not have the power to examine whether laws, regulations and national treaties that have been duly published are enforceable. However, if a court doubts the application of a regulation due to its possible unlawfulness, it

⁵ Book Review: Judicial Review and the Law of the Constitution. by Sylvia Snowiss <https://scholarship.law.umn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1873&context=concomm>.

⁶ <https://law.justia.com/constitution/us/acts-of-congress-held-unconstitutional.html>.

⁷ See: Конституционное право зарубежных стран: учебник для вузов / Под общ. ред. член-корр. РАН, проф. М.В. Баглая, д. ю. н., проф. Ю.И. Лейбо, д. ю. н., проф. Л.М. Энтина.

must submit an application for annulment of the regulation to the Constitutional Court (art. 89 of the Constitution). The Austrian Constitutional Court may only repeal an ordinance as unlawful if a request to repeal it has definitely been made or if the said ordinance would have been applied by the Constitutional Court in its consideration of a legal dispute. In certain cases, the Court may annul an entire judgment as unlawful if it lacks any legal basis, was issued by an incompetent body or was published in an unlawful manner (art. 139 of the Constitution)⁸. In Italy, the Constitutional Court is not considered part of the judiciary system and its status is specified in the section on constitutional guarantees of citizens' rights (art. 134-137 of the Constitution). In fact, the Constitutional Court acts as co-legislator when laws suffer from defects and the Court has to include "additional" or "substitute" provisions⁹. Furthermore, the Spanish Constitution establishes that "the Supreme Court, the jurisdiction of which extends over the whole of Spain, as it is the highest judicial authority in all areas of judicial activity, except for that which concerns constitutional guarantees" (art. 123).

As far as the constitutional control is concerned, the European Constitutions reflect not only the principles of the judiciary but also the principles of judicial procedure and the legal status of constitutional judges¹⁰.

When it comes to the constitutional model of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Uzbekistan is mostly characterized by the European model. A comparative legal analysis of the existence of this model in Uzbekistan and other European countries shows that it differs, above all, from the French model. A different approach is used in France, where constitutional oversight is exercised by a non-judicial body. In particular, the constitutionality of legal acts is checked by various bodies. Laws are checked by the Constitutional Council, and acts of executive power bodies – are by the Council of State.

These structures are not called courts, but quasi-judicial bodies. This is mainly because decisions are made in closed meetings and taken in written form. Despite the differences between the French and Uzbek models, there are some common features within the general European model. As an example, both models are characterised by predominantly ex-ante control.

Therefore, the Uzbek model of constitutional control has similarities with the German and Austrian models. For instance, according to N.A. Veresov, in the Federal Republic of Germany, constitutional control is exercised by the Federal Constitutional Court¹¹. In the same way, as in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Constitutional Court is competent to exercise abstract control as well as to check and determine the constitutionality of laws on ratifying international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan before they are signed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As to differences, the following may be noted: in Germany, examination of a constitutional complaint on violation of rights and freedoms may have both concrete and abstract nature, i.e. outside of a concrete case. Also, the subject of the constitutional complaint itself is not limited to laws but covers other acts issued by public authorities, judicial decisions and administrative acts¹². Consequently, Germany has fewer restrictions in relation to constitutional complaints rather than the Republic of Uzbekistan. Moreover, the FRG has the right to take part in proceedings to remove the highest official from office and to participate in the resolution of international legal disputes. Furthermore, the Federal Constitutional Court has the right to declare parties and public associations unconstitutional, decide on charges against judges of Federal and Land courts, and decide on the validity and loss of membership of members of the Bundestag¹³.

Additionally, it is important to note that the Constitutional Court has the right, upon the request of the President, to examine the constitutionality of an

⁸ https://www.servat.unibe.ch/icl/au00000_.html Comparing Constitutions and International Constitutional Law.

⁹ See: Клишас А.А. Конституционный контроль и конституционное правосудие зарубежных стран. Сравнительно-правовое исследование / Под ред. проф. В. В. Еремина. – М., 2007. С. 15–119; Narutyunyan G., Mavcic A. Constitutional review and its development in the modern world (a comparative constitutional analysis). – Yerevan; Ljubljana, 1999.

¹⁰ <https://www.europeanlawinstitute.eu/membership/institutional-members/swiss-federal-supreme-court/>.

¹¹ See: Вересова Н.А. Нормотворческая функция Федерального Конституционного суда ФРГ и Конституционного суда РФ (сравнительно-правовой анализ). URL: <http://lawtheses.com/normotvorcheskaya-funktsiya-federalnogo-konstitutsionnogo-sudafederativnoy-respubliki-germanii-i-konstitutsionnogo-suda-#ixzz4Z2wI9Rj3>.

¹² https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/DE/Das-Gericht/Aufgaben/aufgaben_node.html.

¹³ See: Основной закон Федеративной Республики Германии // Федеративная Республика Германия. Конституция и законодательные акты. Пер. с нем. / Под ред. Ю.П. Урьяса. – М.: Прогресс, 1991; Приводится по: Конституции государств Европейского Союза / Под общей редакцией Л.А. Окунькова. – М.: НОРМА, 1997. – С. 181–234.

initiative to hold a referendum in the Republic of Uzbekistan prior to the appointment of the President. We should consider that in the FRG the constitutional court of the FRG does not have such a power expressly provided for in the main legal act of the country. From the aforementioned, in most cases, the competence, the procedure of formation and the activities of the specialized body do not coincide in these countries. From our point of view, this phenomenon is due to the

fact that Uzbekistan, when developing the mechanism of constitutional control, has taken into account many different European models and has adopted many features, above all, of German and Austrian and French constitutional justice.

For examining the distinctive features of Constitutional control in the Republic of Uzbekistan and foreign countries from a more detailed perspective, the following table is provided:

The Constitutional control:

Uzbek model	Continental model	American model
1. Implemented by special bodies.	1. Implemented by special bodies.	1. Implemented by all courts.
2. The decisions can not be appealed.	2. The decisions can not be appealed.	2. The decisions made by the courts of common jurisdiction can be appealed by the Supreme Court.
3.Characterised by centralization.	3.Characterised by centralization.	3.Characterized by decentralization.
4. Characterized by the forms of preliminary, abstract and compulsory control.	4. Characterized by the forms of preliminary, abstract and compulsory control.	4. The realization of subsequent and concrete control.
5. The specialized body which is not included in the system of bodies.	5. The specialized body which is not included in the common system of bodies.	5. the Courts exercising constitutional control are included in the common system of General courts.

Coming to the conclusion, the institution of constitutional control plays a crucial and fundamental role in ensuring the supremacy of the Constitution. A comparative legal analysis of the mechanism of constitutional control within the existing models: American and European, is of paramount importance for the improvement of constitutional justice in Uzbekistan. The analysis and study of the European model are of great interest, as the identification of features, similarities and differences

allow us to determine the prospects for the development of constitutional justice in the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the same time, the development of constitutional justice plays an important role in the development of civil society, since the constitutional bodies are recognized as directly protecting human and civil rights and their freedoms. In addition, the stable functioning of constitutional justice bodies is one of the main features of a modern, highly developed state governed by the rule of law.

